

TEACHERS' ATTITUDES AND CHALLENGES TOWARDS USE OF MOTHER TONGUE-BASED INSTRUCTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10973430>

ABSTRACT

This study delves into the attitudes and challenges faced by teachers in implementing mother-tongue-based instruction (MTBI) in Isabela province, Philippines. A comprehensive analysis was conducted based on demographic profiles and survey responses from teachers across various grade levels. Findings reveal a predominant demographic profile among teachers, characterized by ages between 29-33 years, predominantly female, with educational backgrounds encompassing master's units and fluent in the local language, *Iloko*. Overall, teachers exhibited a positive attitude towards MTBI, particularly those teaching in Kindergarten to Grade 3, as evidenced by their agreement with statements related to MTBI principles. Moreover, significant relationships were observed between teachers' attitudes towards MTBI and demographic factors such as age, sex, place of origin, educational background, mother tongue, and years of teaching experience. Finally, teachers identified several challenges hindering effective MTBI implementation, which include resource constraints, translation difficulties, and conflicts between different varieties of mother tongues. These findings underscore the importance of addressing these challenges to enhance the effectiveness of the MTBI program and ensure quality education for all learners.

Keywords: *Teachers' Attitudes, Challenges, Mother tongue, Mother-tongue-based Instruction*

INTRODUCTION

Language in education is a concept clearly defined as it has been established in many studies. Learners particularly young children enter the classroom speaking in one or more languages, depending on their level of skill or proficiency (Walter, 2008). Most children go to school speaking only one primary language, while those in cities usually show some level of bilingualism, according to Baker (2006). Teachers may or may not speak the language(s) that their pupils use in the classroom. The curriculum might be offered in one language but not another, or in a language that neither the teacher nor the pupils are fluent in.

As a result, a learner's educational growth is fundamentally influenced by the language of instruction in a classroom. Language and literacy are seen as socially produced, culturally mediated practices, and they are essential to learning according to Ochs (1986). In other words, choosing the language or languages to teach in schools is an important decision in bilingual and multilingual societies like the Philippines.

Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), an educational policy incorporating more than one language in literacy and instruction, is a recent development in the Philippine educational system. However, according to Nolasco (2008), simply changing the MOI is insufficient to make the MTB-MLE work in the Philippine setting. He identified four critical requirements for the successful implementation of the MTB-MLE program, one of which is community support and empowerment. He also mentioned that one of the reoccurring concerns is teachers' attitudes regarding the mother tongue as a medium of instruction, whether good or negative.

As educators consider the language they employ in the classroom, their attitudes become more apparent. Whether they are aware of it or not, their attitudes have a significant impact on how languages develop, deteriorate, or are restored (Baker, 1988). According to Rillo and Alieto (2018), teachers' attitudes serve as either an enabling or disabling factor in the use of a certain language. Additionally, as a result of their cultural orientation, the teachers have a significant influence on their younger students (Shameem, 2004). Finally, the teacher's preparation should include their attitude toward the resources they will use to teach their courses as well as their knowledge and expertise in that area of expertise (Vizconde, 2006).

According to Sarnoff (1970), attitude is the propensity to respond favorably or unfavorably to a group of objects. The same goes for attitude, which Bohner and Wanke (2002) even went so far as to say typically indicates an evaluation of an object. As a result, attitude can be defined as a cognitive, emotive, and behavioral response to any object. Furthermore, Eagly and Chaiken (1993) hypothesized that attitude can elicit three kinds of responses. The first is cognitive responses, which correspond to an individual's thoughts and beliefs about the object of their attitude. Second, emotional responses that elicit feelings or emotions about the object of an attitude, and third, behavioral responses that entail acts taken to the object of an attitude. These three responses frequently

overlap, making it difficult to distinguish them (Zhang, 2010). However, according to Bohner and Wanke (2002), attitude is commonly described as a summary appraisal of a thought object that may include only one answer type or a combination of two or all three categories.

As a result, an attitude is a hypothetical construct that cannot be directly observed but can be inferred from observed reactions (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). In other words, when specific stimuli, such as the use of the mother tongue in teaching Grades 1–3, elicit responses, a mental state known as attitude is formed.

The success of MTB-MLE being an important component of the K to 12 curriculum lies much in the attitude of teachers towards the language they use for instruction. Such an attitude is crucial in meeting the objectives of mother tongue-based instruction. There have been local studies that explored teachers' attitudes toward mother-tongue-based instruction (Tonio and Ella, 2019; Wa-Mbaleka, 2014; Lartec et al., 2014). These studies dealt as well the problems encountered by the teachers in the implementation of MTBI.

As an elementary teacher, the researcher has observed that her fellow teachers using mother-tongue-based instruction have different feelings toward it. Some are happy but others are not. They also talk about the challenges they meet with using mother tongue in teaching. These are teachers from Kindergarten level to Grade 3. Personally, the researcher sees the importance of Mother Tongue-Based Instruction in early education, believing that it can help pupils learn various concepts. But, she also recognizes the problems or issues that surround the implementation of MTBI which include among others the dearth of instructional materials, lack of training of the teachers, and their lukewarm reception of the use of pupils' mother tongue.

Thus, in consideration of the above, the researcher was prompted to conduct this study. The study aimed at determining the attitudes of teachers toward the use of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3 and the problems they meet when using the mother tongue. The results of the study are deemed beneficial as they will reveal how teachers at the elementary level feel about the use of the mother tongue and the struggles they encounter with it. These pieces of information could later be used for decision-making by higher authorities for important educational programs.

Research Questions

This study investigated the teachers' attitudes toward the use of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3 and the challenges they encounter.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teachers as to:
 - a. age
 - b. sex
 - c. place of origin (province)
 - d. educational background
 - e. mother tongue used

- f. number of years of language teaching experience
 2. What are the attitudes of teachers toward mother-tongue-based instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3?
 3. Is there a relationship between teachers' attitudes towards mother-tongue-based instruction and select variables?
 4. What are the teachers' perceived challenges or problems in using the mother tongue as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3?
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METHODOLOGY

The research design used in the study was descriptive-correlational. The study was conducted in seven (7) elementary schools in the City Schools Division of Ilagan, Isabela. Involved as respondents in this study were basic education teachers in public elementary schools who teach at the kindergarten level, Grade 1, Grade 2, and Grade 3. These teachers use a mother tongue as a medium of instruction.

Before conducting the study or gathering data, the researcher sought the approval of the school heads of the different elementary schools covered in the study. This was done by way of a request letter. After getting the approval, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire and conducted personal interviews with the respondents.

The main instrument to be used in this study was a survey questionnaire adapted from the study of Tonio and Ella (2019) entitled "Pre-Service Teachers' Attitudes toward the Use of Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction" which was published in the Asian EFL Journal. The present study used the instrument as is, finding all the statements fit to Philippine context. Moreover, this questionnaire earned a reliability rating of 0.80 using Cronbach's Alpha when it was used in previous studies.

The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts. In Part 1, respondents were asked to provide pertinent personal information such as gender, age, province, first language, and whether or not their native language is different from the mother tongue identified/declared by the Department of Education for their city or province.

Meanwhile, the fourteen (14) statements included in Part II are of two levels. Level 1 includes items 1-12 which sought the opinions of the teachers on some issues and problems related to teaching and learning in the mother tongue such as the benefits of teaching and learning in the mother tongue to pupils, teachers, and parents, as well as the limitations of instruction in the mother tongue.

On the other hand, Level 2 comprised items 13 and 14 that explore the teachers' readiness to undergo training in mother tongue instruction and their willingness to teach in the mother tongue.

Part III of the questionnaire required the respondents to rank the statements (1-

11) indicating perceived problems in the use of mother tongue-based instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3. They may also add to the list of problems.

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Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, namely: frequency count, mean, mode, and standard deviation. The chi-square test for independence using the SPSS application was to be used to establish the relationship between variables. Moreover, a qualitative approach was employed to analyze the perceived problems in using the mother tongue.

Analysis of data used in determining teachers' attitudes towards the use of mother tongue-based instruction is shown below:

Scale	Range	Description
4	4.00 – 3.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.99 – 2.00	Agree
2	1.99 – 1.00	Disagree
1	1.00 – 0.99	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Teachers

Profile of the teachers in terms of age, sex, educational background, mother tongue used, and language teaching experience is provided and discussed below.

Table 1 presents a diverse age distribution among the respondents. Based on the data, the most common age group among the respondents is 29-33 years old, accounting for 24.24 percent of the total respondents. On the other hand, the least common age group is 34-38 and 44-49 years old, comprising 18.18 percent of the total respondents. The findings suggest that most of the teacher-respondents are already in their late 20's and early 30's. which means that there are more young teachers, as might be expected from the large numbers participating in the Teacher Induction Scheme in recent years.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
24–28	6	18.18
29–33	8	24.24
34–38	6	18.18
39–43	7	21.21
44–49	6	18.18
Total	33	100

These results coincide with the findings of Salvan and Hanbre (2020) indicating that out of 16 teachers who participated, 50% were between 27 and 32 years old. This means that if the starting age of a teacher to enter a teaching profession right after graduation is 21 years old, then these teachers are just developing their teaching profession.

Table 2. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	26	78.79
Male	7	21.21
Total	33	100

It can be gleaned from Table 2 that the survey sample was predominantly composed of females, with 26 out of 33 respondents which is approximately 79 percent. In contrast, males made up a smaller proportion, accounting for only around 21 percent of the total respondents. The analysis highlights a pronounced gender disparity among the survey respondents, with females comprising the majority of the sample. The results suggest that there are more female teachers since it has been viewed that education is a female-dominated profession.

Globally, women are over-represented in the teaching force. And their numbers are rising: Since 2015, globally, the proportion of female teachers has increased across primary, lower, and upper secondary levels. In pre-primary education, women make up 94% of the teaching force. But at higher levels of education, their numbers dwindle. Women make up 68% of the teaching force in primary, 58% at lower secondary, 52% at upper secondary, and 43% at tertiary level (UNESCO, 2023). In contrast, Statista Research Department which published data in October 2022, showed that the employment rates of males and females worldwide since 2000. Employment rates of males have been consistently higher than women, the gap barely narrowing in the two decades. In 2000, the employment rate for males was around 73% compared to nearly 48% for females. Trends slightly decreased for both genders till 2019, after which there was a significant decline in 2020. The rates for both genders increased till 2022 (67.86% for males and 43.82% for females) but were overall lower than in 2000. However, the gender gap in employment rates remained approximately the same over the years (Zoe

Talent Solutions, 2024). Additionally, an article published that in 2022, 67.9 percent of men ages 25 and older were employed, compared with 55.4 percent of women.

While men have higher employment-population ratios than women at every level of educational attainment, the gap between men and women becomes smaller as educational attainment increases (The Economics Daily, 2023).

Table 3. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of place of origin (Province)

Place of Origin (Province)	Frequency	Percentage
Cagayan	1	3.00
Isabela	32	97.00
Total	33	100

As shown in Table 3, the majority of the respondents, constituting 97.00%, were from Isabela province. Only a small fraction, accounting for 3.00%, were from Cagayan province. This means that the Isabela province has a significantly higher representation compared to Cagayan.

Table 4 contains data on the frequency and percentage distributions of respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment. The majority of the respondents, comprising 76%, completed some units toward a Master's degree. This suggests that a significant portion of the respondents have pursued further education beyond their bachelor's degree but have not necessarily completed their master's program. On the contrary, individuals holding doctorate degrees comprised the smallest subset of respondents, accounting for only 3% of the total.

Table 4. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of educational background

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage
Baccalaureate Degree Holder	3	9
With Master's Units	25	76
Master's Graduate	4	12
Doctorate Degree Holder	1	3.00
Total	33	100

The results suggest that the surveyed population is predominantly composed of individuals who have pursued or are in the process of pursuing higher education beyond the bachelor's level, with the majority having completed or partially completed Master's level education.

The results are in agreement with the results of a study that revealed that 66.7 percent (67%) of the teachers were pursuing their master's degree program. About 17

percent (17%) of them have either obtained their master's degree or are pursuing doctorate programs. Teachers are required to participate in professional development sessions and take additional college courses to maintain their current certification. Getting a master's degree at the beginning of a teaching career gives educators more flexibility when it comes to choosing later courses. This also provides educators with an opportunity to take even higher-level courses, work toward a doctorate in education, and connect with other experts in the field (Salvan and Hanbre, 2020).

Table 5. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of mother tongue used

Mother Tongue Used	Frequency	Percentage
Iloko	21	64.00
Tagalog/Filipino	11	33.00
Ybanag	1	3.00
Total	33	100

As shown in Table 5 above, the majority of respondents, comprising 64.00 percent, used Iloko as their mother tongue. This indicates a significant presence of Iloko speakers within the surveyed population. Tagalog/Filipino speakers represented 33.00 percent of the respondents, constituting a substantial but smaller portion than Iloko speakers. Ybanag speakers were the least represented, accounting for only 3.00 percent of the respondents. This means that Ilocano is the language spoken by a majority of the people in Isabela.

Isabela today is home to, 1,593,566 people who are distinguished for their resilience and diligence. The majority of them are classified as Ilocanos, who constitute 69% of total households. Two other prominent ethnolinguistic groups are Ybanag at 14% and Tagalog at 10%. The balance of 7% belongs to the *Gaddang, Paranan, Yogad*, and other indigenous tribes (The Official Website of the Province of Isabela, 2023).

Table 6. Frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers in terms of the number of years of language teaching experience

Number of Years of Language Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1–3	5	15.15
4–6	10	30.30
7–9	8	24.24
10–12	10	30.30
Total	33	100

As seen in the above data (Table 6), most of the respondents fell within the 4-6 and 10-12 years categories. The categories of 4–6 years and 10–12 years of experience each comprised 30.30 percent of the respondents, indicating a prevalence of mid-career

language teachers within the sample. This suggests that a substantial portion of the respondents have attained a moderate to advanced level of experience in language teaching, possibly reflecting a stable or established phase in their career. There were only five (5) teachers or approximately 15 percent of the respondents who were in the range of 1-3 years in service. This implies that among the 33 respondents, there are very few of them who are new in the teaching profession.

Research shows that, on average, teachers with more than years of experience are more effective than teachers with no experience, but are not much more effective than those with 5 years of experience (Ladd, 2008). Studies have also documented some evidence that effectiveness declines after some point, particularly among high school teachers. In fact, evidence suggests that the most experienced high school mathematics teachers greater than (25 years) may be less effective than their less experienced counterparts (Ladd, 2008) and even their inexperienced colleagues (Harris and Sass, 2007).

Attitudes of Teachers towards Mother-Tongue-Based Instruction

The attitudes of teachers towards mother-tongue-based instruction are revealed in the following table.

Table 7. Attitudes of teachers towards Mother-Tongue-Based Instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3

Indicators	Mean	Sd	Description
1. A policy on the use of mother tongue in the Philippine primary schools (Grades 1-3) is good in principle.	2.90	0.94	Agree
2. It is possible to teach all primary school subjects from Grades 1-3 in the mother tongue or language of the local community.	2.69	1.01	Agree
3. It is possible to teach my subjects completely in mother tongue.	2.60	0.86	Agree
4. Teaching in their mother tongue will enable teachers to express themselves clearly in class.	2.87	0.92	Agree
5. Teaching in mother tongue will enable pupils to understand easily.	2.81	1.04	Agree
6. It will make lessons interesting to pupils.	2.97	0.77	Agree
7. It will enable children to perform well in the English language in the future.	2.30	0.81	Disagree
8. It will enable parents to participate in the education of their children.	3.03	0.58	Agree
9. All technical terms and expressions in my subject area(s) can be easily translated into mother tongue.	2.27	1.03	Disagree

10. Textbooks for teaching my subjects can easily be produced in mother tongue.	2.27	0.62	Disagree
11. My education and training, which have been in English, will not interfere with my teaching children in mother tongue.	2.81	0.76	Agree
12. The use of mother tongue in teaching will degrade the teaching profession in the Philippines.	2.00	0.70	Disagree
13. I am willing to undergo any special training that will enable me to teach in mother tongue.	3.18	0.88	Agree
14. I am willing to teach in mother tongue.	2.93	0.74	Agree
Overall Mean	2.69		Agree

As shown in Table 8, statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 11, 13 and 14 obtained a weighted mean of 2.909, 2.697, 2.606, 2.879, 2.818, 2.970, 3.030, 2.818, 3.182, and 2.939 respectively with a description of “Agree”. On the contrary, statements 7, 9, 10, and 12 earned a weighted mean of 2.303, 2.273, 2.273, and 2.00 respectively with a description of “Disagree.”

Based on the findings above, it can be said that the teachers believe that a policy on the use of mother tongue in primary schools (Kindergarten to Grade III) is a good principle. It is because they can teach all primary school subjects from Kindergarten to Grade III in the mother tongue or language of the local community. Moreover, the teachers see the possibility of teaching their subjects completely in mother tongue because doing so will enable them to express themselves clearly in class which results in having students understand easily the lessons. Lessons become interesting to pupils.

It is in the teachers’ view that by using the mother tongue, parents can participate in their children’s education. They likewise believe that their English education and training will not interfere with their teaching using mother tongue. As they recognize the intricacy of using the mother tongue of their pupils with which they are unfamiliar, they are willing to undergo training to enable them to teach in mother tongue. This willingness to learn their mother tongue is backed further by their positive attitude toward their willingness to teach in their mother tongue.

The teachers’ negative attitude toward the use of the mother tongue is exemplified by their reservation that the mother tongue will enable children to perform well in the English language in the future. They also disagree that all technical terms and expressions in their subject areas could be easily translated into mother tongue. In like manner, they do not believe that the textbooks they use in teaching their subjects could be easily produced in mother tongue. Although they see problems in using mother tongue, they do not believe that the use of it would degrade or lower the teaching profession in the Philippines.

The study's findings are consistent with those of two local studies, Tonio and Ella (2019) and Wa-Mbaleka (2014), which showed that English teachers thought MTB-MLE

would help improve mother tongue acquisition but not English language proficiency. The study conducted by Tonio (2019) and Lartec et al. (2014) revealed that the main issues encountered by teachers in implementing mother-tongue based instruction are lack of textbooks, vocabulary, and teacher-training. Meanwhile, the teachers' negative attitude toward the availability of textbooks, the possibility of concrete translation and vocabulary, and the compatibility of teachers' education and training are supported by these findings.

The current study's findings are also similar to Tonio and Ella's (2019) findings, indicating that respondents in both studies believe that using mother tongue would neither degrade or lower the teaching profession in the Philippines.

The results of this study, along with those of other foreign studies, are in opposition to those of Ejieh (2004), who found that student teachers generally had a negative attitude toward the teaching and training of mother tongue in elementary schools.

On the other hand, the results of this study demonstrating teachers' generally positive attitudes toward the use of mother tongue as a medium of instruction are corroborated by a study by Adesina and Okewole (2014), also in Nigeria, which involved teachers' opinions on mother tongue instruction in nursery schools.

Overall, teachers in Kindergarten to Grade 3 “agreed” to the use of mother-tongue-based instruction (MTBI) with an overall mean of 2.69, indicating a positive attitude. This is opposed to the findings of Andrino & Arsenal (2019) where the respondents exhibited a negative attitude towards teaching mother tongue in basic education.

Relationship between Teachers' Attitudes toward Mother-Tongue-Based Instruction and Select Variables

The table below exhibits the relationship between the teacher's attitudes toward mother-tongue-based instruction when grouped by the selected variables. ambiguous

Table 8. Relationship between the teacher's attitudes toward Mother-Tongue Based Instruction and select variables

Profile Variable	Regression Analysis							Remarks
	ρ -Value	Computed Value	ρ -Value	T	R	R ²	Decision	
Age	0.0026	10.6981	0.0000	5.9319	0.2566	0.5065	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex								
Place of Origin								
Educational Background								
Mother Tongue								

No. of Years of Language Teaching								
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The low p -value = 0.0026 suggests that there is strong evidence against the null hypothesis, indicating that the observed data are unlikely to have occurred if the null hypothesis were true. The computed value 10.6981 represents some specific statistic calculated in the analysis. The correlation coefficient R of 0.2566 indicates a weak positive linear relationship between the variables. The R -squared value 0.5065 suggests that approximately 50.65 percent of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable(s).

Given the significant result and rejection of the null hypothesis, there is evidence to support an alternative hypothesis or the presence of a relationship between the variables under consideration. This suggests that there is a moderate correlation between the predicted data and the observed data.

The above findings are contradicted by the results of the study of Tonio and Ella (2019) where the age and sex of the pre-service teachers were found to have no significant relationship with their attitudes toward the use of mother-tongue-based instruction. However, in the same study, place of origin was found to have a relationship with MTBI.

From the findings above, it can be surmised that the attitudes of the teachers toward the use of mother-tongue-based instruction are influenced by their age, sex, place of origin, educational background, mother tongue, and number of years of language teaching experience.

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in the Use of Mother-Tongue-Based Instruction

Table 9 reveals the teachers' perceived challenges or problems in using the mother tongue as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3.

Table 9. Problems or challenges perceived by teachers in the use of Mother-Tongue as a medium of instruction in Kindergarten to Grade 3

Perceived Challenges/Problems	Rank
a. Difficulty in translation	2
b. Difficulty in teaching the different varieties of MT	3
c. Degradation of English language proficiency	8
d. Difference in teacher's and pupils' L1	4
e. Lack of textbooks, references and instructional materials	1
f. Lack of teachers' training in teaching mother tongue	7
g. Low teachers' proficiency in mother tongue	9
h. Low pupils' proficiency in mother tongue	6

i. Incompatibility of MT used by pupils and of MT assigned by DepEd	5
j. Language barrier for transferees and pupils with different L1	10
k. Resistance of parents to using MT as a medium of instruction	11

As evident in the data presented, the problem of “*Lack of textbooks, references, and instructional materials*” ranked first. This challenge suggests a significant barrier to effective instruction in the mother tongue. Insufficient resources can hinder lesson planning, curriculum implementation, and student engagement. It explains thus why the teachers showed negative attitude towards the easy production of textbooks which they can use to teach their subjects. The above findings are consistent with local studies like that of Lartec, et.al (2014) which showed that teachers teaching mother tongue encountered difficulties due to the absence of books written in mother tongue, and of Valerio (2015) indicating teachers’ uncertainty with the instructional materials they use due to lack of localized translation of these materials.

“*Difficulty in translation*” was second in rank. This implies that translation challenges can impede the smooth transition of content from one language to another, affecting comprehension and instructional quality. The teachers have difficulty explaining concepts or lessons in subjects like Math, Science, *Araling Panlipunan* (AP), Music Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH), etc. using mother tongue. Difficulty is specifically encountered in the translation of technical terms and Math concepts (Tonio and Ella, 2019). Because some English terms have no exact translation or equivalents in mother tongue, the teachers have to resort to English (Medilo, 2016).

The teachers’ difficulty in translation accounts for their negative attitude towards it. They are uncertain whether all technical terms and expressions in their subject area(s) can be easily translated into mother tongue.

Another perceived problem that ranked third was the teachers’ “*Difficulty in teaching the different varieties of mother tongue*”. This indicates that variations in the mother tongue spoken by students can pose challenges for teachers in accommodating diverse linguistic backgrounds, potentially affecting instructional effectiveness. This problem relates to other two identified problems, namely the “lack of teachers’ training in teaching mother tongue”, and the “lack of textbooks, references, and instructional materials.”

Similarly, the “*Difference in teacher’s and pupils’ L1* ” was also perceived by teachers as a challenge. They ranked this problem as fourth among the different perceived challenges. This suggests that discrepancies between the language proficiency levels of teachers and students may hinder effective communication and instruction, impacting learning outcomes. Differences between a teacher's and pupils' first language (L1) can indeed pose challenges in mother-tongue-based instruction. When the teacher and students do not share the same L1, communication barriers may arise,

hindering effective instruction and learning. These barriers can manifest in various forms, such as difficulty in conveying complex concepts, misunderstanding instructions, and challenges in providing feedback.

A study by Cummins (2000) highlights how language differences between teachers and students can impede comprehension and engagement in the classroom. Cummins emphasizes the importance of utilizing students' mother tongue in instruction to bridge these gaps and facilitate better learning outcomes.

“Incompatibility of mother tongue used by pupils and of mother tongue assigned by DepEd” occupied Rank 5 in the teachers' perceived challenges. Misalignment between the mother tongue spoken by students and the one designated by the Department of Education can create confusion and hinder effective instruction.

Moreover, ranked 6 as the perceived challenge was the *“Low pupils' proficiency in the mother tongue”*. This implies that the limited proficiency in the mother tongue among students may hinder their ability to fully engage with instructional materials and comprehend lesson content.

Ranked 7th was *“Lack of teachers' training in teaching mother tongue”*. Insufficient training and professional development opportunities for teachers can result in ineffective instructional strategies and limited support for students' language development.

“Degradation of English language proficiency” was ranked 8. To some, teaching children using mother tongue can contribute to lack of English proficiency. It could mean that an increased focus on the mother tongue may lead to neglect or a decline in English language proficiency, which could have broader implications for students' academic and future opportunities. The same problem was found in Ejie's (2004) study in Nigeria where the use of mother tongue harmed English learning.

Ranked 9 was the *“Low teachers' proficiency in the mother tongue”*. Limited proficiency among teachers in the mother tongue may compromise their ability to effectively convey lesson content and support students' language development. This problem is related to difficulty in translation (Tonio and Ella, 2019). Teachers experience hard time expressing themselves in the mother tongue understood by the students because of a lack of training and unfamiliarity with the language.

Positioned in the 10th place was the *“Language barrier for transferees and pupils with different L1”*. Students who transfer from other regions or have a different first language may face challenges in adapting to instruction conducted in the mother tongue, potentially affecting their academic progress. This is another problem met by the teachers. Adjusting to the L1 of transfer students is an added burden for them.

In the 11th rank was the *“Resistance of parents in using mother tongue as a medium of instruction”*. Because many parents do not understand the importance of using mother tongue as a medium of instruction, they object to its use. In an interview with the

parents, they are opposed to using mother tongue as MOI because they believe that it will not help their children acquire English proficiency. Indeed, parental resistance can undermine efforts to implement mother tongue-based instruction, affecting support systems and community engagement.

As presented in the table, these perceived challenges underscore the complexities involved in implementing mother tongue-based instruction in early education settings, highlighting the importance of addressing resource limitations, linguistic diversity, teacher training, and community engagement to ensure effective language learning and educational outcomes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings presented in this study, several key conclusions can be drawn. First, the demographic profile of teachers involved in the implementation of mother-tongue-based instruction (MTBI) reveals a predominantly female, mid-career group from Isabela province, with a significant portion holding master's units and speaking *Iloko*. Second, the positive attitudes exhibited by teachers towards MTBI, particularly in Kindergarten to Grade 3, signify a readiness to embrace this instructional approach. However, the presence of challenges, such as the lack of essential resources and difficulties in translation and language variation, underscores the need for targeted support and interventions. Furthermore, the identified relationship between teachers' attitudes towards MTBI and various demographic factors emphasizes the importance of considering individual characteristics in the successful implementation of MTBI. Finally, addressing these challenges and leveraging the positive attitudes of teachers toward MTBI are crucial steps toward enhancing its effectiveness and promoting inclusive and culturally responsive education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the study on mother-tongue-based instruction (MTBI) implementation recommends the following:

1. The Department of Education (DepEd) is encouraged to address the identified shortage of textbooks, references, and instructional materials by allocating adequate resources to schools implementing MTBI. This may involve collaborating with publishers and educational organizations to develop and distribute materials tailored to various mother tongues.

2. Targeted training and professional development programs for teachers should be offered to enhance their translation skills, teach different varieties of mother tongues, and

effectively integrate MTBI into their classrooms. These programs should also address the specific needs and challenges identified among teachers of different demographics.

3. The Department of Education should ensure alignment between the mother tongue used by the learners and that what it assigned. This may involve reviewing and adapting curriculum guidelines to reflect the linguistic diversity of students while maintaining consistency with educational standards. Language mapping is highly recommended.

4. Support networks or communities of practice where teachers can share experiences, resources, and best practices related to MTBI implementation have to be established by schools through the support of DepEd. Encouraging collaboration and knowledge exchange among educators can help address common challenges and promote continuous improvement.

5. Teachers in the elementary level particularly those using MTBI are encouraged to conduct further research to better understand the impact of MTBI on student learning outcomes, linguistic development, and cultural identity. Continuous evaluation of MTBI programs is essential to identify areas for improvement and inform evidence-based decision-making.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares adherence to ethical standards in research, i.e., she followed all procedures and methodologies with utmost integrity, transparency, and respect for the rights and welfare of all participants involved. Prior to the conduct of the study, informed consent was obtained from the participants. Furthermore, there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. The researcher also ensured that plagiarism was strictly avoided, that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings of the study, and that the results were used solely for the study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher is deeply grateful to all who participated in the study, particularly the teachers of Kindergarten to Grade 3 levels in the City Schools Division of Ilagan, Department of Education who served as respondents, for their support and cooperation. The same acknowledgment is given to school heads who allowed their teachers to actively get involved in the research.

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